

A Comparative Study of Effects of Combined Intraperitoneal and Port-Site Infiltration of Bupivacaine versus Ropivacaine on Postoperative Pain after Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy: A Randomised Trial

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Abstract:

Introduction: This study was conducted to compare the efficacy of ropivacaine and bupivacaine using a combined intraperitoneal and port-site administration to reduce the postoperative pain in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Materials and Methods: Eighty patients scheduled for elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy with symptomatic cholelithiasis, 18-65 years, either gender, American society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) class I and II, were included. Patients were allocated into two groups of 40 each after randomization. Group R patients were given 0.375% Ropivacaine 35 mL [25 mL intraperitoneal plus 10 mL at port-site], while Group B patients were given 0.25% Bupivacaine 35 mL [25 mL intraperitoneal plus 10 mL at port-site]. Noninvasive blood pressure (NIBP), SpO₂, Heart rate (HR), Respiratory rate (RR), Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) score and rescue analgesia were noted in post-operative period, at intervals of 0, 1, 2, 4, 8, 12 and 24 hours respectively.

Results: The demographic and clinical differences between two groups were not significant. The mean HR was comparable in both the groups, except at 12th hour post-operatively where Group R had significantly lower heart rate. The mean SBP was also comparable between the two groups, other than the 4th and 12th hour respectively, Group R values being significantly lower. The mean Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP) showed a significant reduction in Group R at 8th and 12th hour respectively. At all the time-intervals the VAS score was lower in Group R, up to 12th Hour, at the 12th hour significantly lower VAS scores were observed. In Group R a significantly lower number of rescue analgesia with a longer time for first dose of rescue analgesia was seen during the 24-hour postoperative period.

Conclusion: In the early postoperative period as compared to 0.25% bupivacaine, 0.375% of ropivacaine provided good quality analgesia, having no adverse effects with less consumption of postoperative supplemental analgesics and can be incorporated in routine practice.

Keywords: Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy; Bupivacaine; Ropivacaine, Postoperative Pain.

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Introduction

Cholecystectomy is one of the commonly performed surgical procedures and in the present era laparoscopic cholecystectomy is fast replacing open surgery. Being minimally invasive, and less traumatic it offers the benefits of faster recovery, reduced hospital stay, lower mortality and cost and time as it can be performed as a day care surgery.

[1] The aetiology of pain following laparoscopic cholecystectomy is multifactorial and includes incisional pain, visceral pain, parietal pain due to trauma of diaphragm and peritoneum and shoulder tip pain as a result of pneumoperitoneum. [2] Providing optimal pain relief is an important

concern as poorly controlled postoperative pain leads to a delayed recovery, increased need for opioid analgesics, higher morbidity, and longer time to discharge and chronic pain NSAIDs and opioids used parenterally constitute the most common method for postoperative pain relief. Using lower abdominal inflation pressures and replacing carbon dioxide with nitrous oxide for pneumoperitoneum have been tried. Local anaesthetic infiltration to port site as well as intraperitoneal route are an alternative to parenteral drugs and are free of side effects like gastritis, nausea, vomiting and pruritus seen with parenteral

drugs. [3] Bupivacaine is a long acting amide local anaesthetic routinely used but is associated with cardiotoxicity following inadvertent intravascular injection. Ropivacaine, an S-enantiomer of bupivacaine, has a better safety profile compared to bupivacaine in terms of cardiotoxicity. Studies in the past have compared placebo with intraperitoneal local anaesthetic or port –site infiltration of local anaesthetics with intraperitoneal infiltration. [4,5,6,7,8,9,10] Very few studies have been undertaken comparing combined port site and intraperitoneal infiltration with bupivacaine and ropivacaine for postoperative analgesia following laparoscopic cholecystectomy and they differ in their outcomes. [11] Hence this study was conducted.

Materials and Methods

This was a prospective randomised double blinded study. Institutional ethical committee approval, informed written consent from the patients were obtained before enrollment for the study. 80 patients of either sex, aged between 18-65 yrs of ASA 1 and 2, undergoing elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy under general anaesthesia were allotted randomly into two groups using a computer generated random table.

Group R (40 patients) received ropivacaine 0.375% and group B received bupivacaine 0.25%, 35ml each. The sample size calculation was done based on the expected difference in the scores of the two groups, the significance level and the power of study were taken as 1.96 and 0.84 respectively and with a 0.5 expected difference in the VAS scores between the groups and 0.6 as pooled standard deviation the required sample size was 37.6 and was rounded off to 40. Those with comorbidities like hypertension and diabetes mellitus, allergy to local anaesthetics and acute cholecystitis were excluded from the study.

Preanesthetic evaluation which included a detailed history and a general physical examination, systemic examination, airway and spine assessment was done on the day prior to the surgery. Routine investigations like blood grouping, complete haemogram, random blood sugar, renal function tests, liver function tests, x ray were done and if necessary other relevant investigations were ordered.

All the patients were explained about the general anaesthesia procedure and how to quantify pain using VAS scale. Patients were kept nil orally for 8-10 hours and oral tablet ranitidine 150mg and tablet alprazolam 0.5mg were given on the night before surgery. On the day of surgery, after shifting the patient to the operating table and securing intravenous (IV) access with an 18G cannula, maintenance fluid of DNS 10ml/kg was started.

Non-invasive monitors that included ECG, SPO₂, NIBP were connected and basal values noted. Following preoxygenation with 100% oxygen and IV premedication with injection Glycopyrrolate 0.01mg/kg, Midazolam 0.05mg/kg and pentazocine 0.5mg/kg, anaesthesia was induced with propofol 2 mg/kg IV and intubation was done after relaxation with succinylcholine 2mg/kg IV. Anaesthesia was maintained with N₂O: O₂(3:2) and isoflurane(0.6-1.5%) and incremental vecuronium 0.05mg/kg was used for intraoperative relaxation.

Intraoperative monitoring of HR, NIBP, SPO₂ and ETCO₂ were done and ventilation adjusted to maintain an ETCO₂ between 25-35mmHg with the patient in 15-20 degree reverse Trendelenburg position and left sided tilt. Pneumoperitoneum was created using CO₂ and intra-abdominal pressure was maintained between 12-15mmHg. After the removal of gallbladder and once hemostasis was obtained, residual blood, fluid and CO₂ were thoroughly suctioned.

Before deflation of pneumoperitoneum, 25ml of 0.25% bupivacaine or 0.375% ropivacaine as per group allocation was infiltrated by the surgeon in the right sub diaphragmatic space, near and above the hepatoduodenal ligament and above gallbladder bed through a catheter inserted via subcostal port under direct vision. Additional 10 ml of study drug was infiltrated around the port-site by the operating surgeon using a 10ml syringe. The time of local anaesthetic administration was noted. Reversal with glycopyrrolate 0.01mg/kg and neostigmine 0.05mg/kg was done and patients were extubated once they met the extubation criteria.

Postoperatively, the following parameters were assessed.

- Abdominal pain at 0hr (immediately after surgery), 1,2,4,8,12 and 24 hours respectively.
- Timing (in minutes) and total number of rescue analgesia given in 24 hours was noted.
- IV Diclofenac 75mg was given when VAS score was more than 4.
- Adverse effects like postoperative nausea and vomiting, shoulder pain, hypotension, pruritus and rash were noted if any.

Results

The data collected were analysed using SPSS software version 26. Results are reported as mean±standard deviation or proportion or percentages as appropriate.

Chi square test and Fisher's exact test was applied and a P value <0.05 is considered statistically significant. Both the groups were similar with respect to age, weight, sex and ASA class.

Table 1: Comparison of demographic data

Demographics	Group R	Group B	P value
Mean age (years)	37.5	34.85	0.26(NS)
Mean weight (kgs)	60.6	56.83	0.15(NS)
Sex (percentages)	Female-55 Male-45	Female-56.3 Male-43.8	0.82(NS)
ASA grade (percentage)	1-65, 2-35	1-70 2-30	0.63(NS)

Hemodynamic variables:

Oxygen saturation: The SPO2 recorded at all the specified time intervals were comparable between the groups and there was no statistical significant difference. It remained above 98% in both the groups at all times.

Heart rate: The heart rate measured using ECG at the specified time intervals was similar between the groups except at 12 hours postoperatively where the patients in the bupivacaine group had a significantly higher heart rate than those in the ropivacaine group. (85.6±7.78, 80.65±5.66, P Value 0.002)

Graph 1: Comparison of Heart rate (HR) between the study groups

Blood pressure: The mean systolic pressure in both the groups was between 125 to 133mmHg at all the specified times and the mean diastolic pressure was between 78 to 86 mmHg. The systolic BP was found to be significantly lower in the ropivacaine group compared to bupivacaine group at 4 hours and 12 hours postoperatively (130.3±6.19,

132.8±4.57, P value <0.04 and 126.1±6.9, 131.05±3.71, P Value 0.001). There was a statistically significant increase in diastolic blood pressure in the bupivacaine group compared to the ropivacaine group at 8 hours and 12 hours postoperatively (85.75±4.13,81.75±4.03, P value and 0.001. 83.75±4.88,78.25±6.83, P Value 0.001).

Graph 2: Comparison of Systolic blood pressure (SBP) between the study groups

Graph 3: Comparison of Diastolic (DBP) between the study groups

Assessment of pain using visual analogue scale (VAS): The VAS scores in group B were significantly higher than group R at 12hrs postoperatively (3.08 ± 1.29 , 2.33 ± 0.94 , P value 0.004). At all the remaining time intervals, patients in group R showed a lower value of VAS score compared to group B.

Table 2: Comparison of Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) scores between the study groups

VAS score	Group R	Group B	P value
0 hour	1.98	2.13	0.39
1 hour	2.83	3.13	0.16
2 hours	3.58	4	0.11
4 hours	4	4.58	0.07
8 hours	3.55	3.68	0.51
12 hours	2.33	3.08	0.004
24 hours	1.4	1.38	0.90

Rescue analgesia requirements and timings: The mean number of rescue analgesia administered during 24hrs period in group B was 1.43 ± 0.55 and in group R was 0.8 ± 0.52 , being higher and significant statistically in group B. (P value <0.001)

Graph4: Comparison of total number of rescue analgesia between the study groups

The mean time for first dose of rescue analgesia was delayed in group R compared to group B but not statistically significant. (4.13 ± 2.81 , 3.34 ± 1.58 , $P=0.14$)

Adverse effects: Only one patient in group R had an episode of PONV and one patient in group R and two patients in group B complained of shoulder pain in the postoperative period. None of the patients had hypotension, pruritus or rash.

Discussion

The most commonly used local anaesthetic for intra peritoneal infiltration from last three decades is bupivacaine. [7,12] Ropivacaine anS -enantiomer of bupivacaine with analgesic effects similar to bupivacaine but reduced risk of cardiac and neurotoxicity, is an attractive alternative to bupivacaine [13] 35ml of both drugs (87.5mg of bupivacaine and 131.25 mg of ropivacaine) was used in our study. The potency ratio of bupivacaine to ropivacaine being 1:1.5. 0.25% of bupivacaine and 0.375% of ropivacaine were used and was well below the toxic level (2 mg/kg for bupivacaine and 4 mg /kg for ropivacaine). [14] We administered the local anaesthetic intraperitoneally and at the port-site at the end of surgery though there are no credible guidelines regarding timing, some studies administering at the start [2,4], while most administering at the end of procedure. [15,16,17]

In our study there was no difference in the hemodynamics between both groups except at 12 hours where the heart rate was significantly lower in the ropivacaine group than the bupivacaine group and the overall heart rate was lower in the ropivacaine group at all the time intervals.

In a study by Meena R K et al [15] comparing intraperitoneal instillation of 0.5 % bupivacaine with 0.75% ropivacaine, a significantly lower heart rate for longer duration was seen in ropivacaine group probably due to more dense and prolonged analgesia. The mean systolic BP was significantly

lower in the ropivacaine group at 4 hours and 12 hours and could be due to better analgesia. Singh et al [10], Sharma et al [11] found no significant difference in blood pressure and the reason could not be ascertained.

The mean VAS score was lower in the ropivacaine group at all the time intervals of the 12 hours postoperatively being significantly lower at 12th hr compared to the bupivacaine group demonstrating the prolonged postoperative analgesia obtained by ropivacaine administration.

In a study by Canon kukuk et al [18] intraperitoneal instillation of 150mg of ropivacaine significantly reduced the VAS score of 1st, 2nd and 12th postoperative hours. When compared with 100 mg bupivacaine or 100mg ropivacaine.

Neha T Das et al [16] reported a prolonged duration of postoperative analgesia with ropivacaine when comparing intraperitoneal instillation of 35ml of 0.375% ropivacaine with 35 ml of 0.25% of bupivacaine in a patient undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

The total number of rescue analgesia administered in the 24hrs postoperatively as diclofenac 75mg intravenously when the VAS scores >4 was significantly less in the ropivacaine group compared to bupivacaine group.

Goldstein A et al [17] conducted a study comparing the 24hr morphine consumption in a patient receiving 20 ml of normal saline, bupivacaine 0.25% or ropivacaine 0.75% instilling intraperitoneally at the end of the surgery and found a lesser morphine consumption in a patient receiving either bupivacaine 0.5% or ropivacaine 0.75% compared to those receiving only normal saline and concluded that local anaesthetics instillation at the end of the surgery reduces the postoperative pain and morphine requirement.

Dan-shu et al [19] evaluated analgesic efficacy of intraperitoneal and incisional site ropivacaine

injected at the end of the laparoscopic cholecystectomy by comparing with the only intraperitoneal and only incisional administration and concluded that combined administration showed a more powerful analgesic effect, reduced morphine consumption postoperatively with a lower incidence of PONV and reduced duration of stay in the post anaesthesia care unit.

Patients in the bupivacaine group required first dose of rescue analgesia earlier than those in ropivacaine group and was statistically significant suggesting a prolonged pain relief in the ropivacaine group and is similar to observations of Meena R.K. et al [15] With respect to adverse effects only one patient in the ropivacaine group had PONV, two patients in the bupivacaine group and one patient in the ropivacaine group had shoulder pain postoperatively suggesting the role of intraperitoneal instillation of local anaesthetics in reducing incidence of PONV and shoulder pain in laparoscopic surgeries.

A meta analysis in 2015 by Choi G J et al [20] showed a significant reduction in the incidence and severity of postoperative shoulder pain in a patient undergoing laparoscopic surgeries. None of the patients had hypotension, rash, pruritus and affecting the safety of local anaesthetics used.

Conclusion

The technique of combined intraperitoneal and port site infiltration of local anaesthetics is an easy cost effective and minimally invasive method to provide postoperative analgesics in those undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomies. Ropivacaine 0.375% provides prolonged analgesia when compared to bupivacaine 0.25% without any adverse effects, with a reduced supplemental analgesics requirement and can be routinely used in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

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